

What Drives Firms' Integration into Global Value Chains: Evidence from Developing Countries

Payal Adlakha* and Durairaj Kumarasamy

*Department of Economics, SBSS, Manav Rachna International Institute of
Research and Studies, Faridabad, Haryana India*

Prakash Singh

*Department of General Management & Public Policy
Goa Institute of Management, Poriem, Sattari, Goa, India*

Abstract: Global value chains play an important role in the upgradation of industrial sectors and economic growth, especially in developing countries. Yet, there are limited studies for developing countries that investigate the factors that influence enterprises' integration in the GVC. Thus, this study looks into the factors such as the firms' nature and their possibility of getting into GVCs, and it focuses on the contextual and organizational characteristics - country-wise and region-wise. We use the World Bank Enterprises survey (WBES) data from 2006 to 2025. The findings reveal that as the size of the firm increases, the participation of firms in GVC increases. Manufacturing firms are more connected, illustrating the significance of firms in the trade. On the contrary, service sector firms are expanding progressively through their GVC linkages. In developing economies, the fundamental factors that promote the likelihood are export orientation, foreign ownership, innovation, and financial accessibility. Conversely, the regional difference shows how the institutional quality, soft and hard infrastructure and trade policies affect the global participation of the firm. Results show that boosting the skills, improving the sectoral competition and a stronger business environment play a crucial role for SMEs in developing to integrate and sustain in the GVCs.

Keywords: Developing Countries, Sustainability, Global Value Chains, Enterprises Survey

JEL Classification Number: F15, F18, F23, F64, F64, O31, O32, O35

1. Introduction

International trade and globalization have transformed into a new approach to development known as Global Value Chains (GVC), which is considered a significant mechanism to stimulate economic growth and advancement, particularly in developing nations. According to the World Bank (2020), there has been a notable rise and expansion of GVC across various economic sectors. GVC primarily stems from multinational corporations aiming to enhance production and marketing efficiency, reduce costs, and achieve global integration (Baldwin and Venables, 2013; OECD, 2013). Several

* Corresponding author. Research Scholar, Email: payaladlakha05121996@gmail.com

researchers have described GVC as ‘a range of process that enables the production of goods and services from conception to completion and delivered to the final consumer, including the after-sales support’ (Gereffi and Fernandez-Stark, 2011; Porter, 1985) .

The global value chain offers several advantages for entire economies and individual firms. Enhanced globalization has allowed the firm to leverage its location strategically to segment production processes for greater cost efficiency by shifting some production phases to lower-cost regions. Consequently, the geographical location of firms is a vital facilitator for breaking down the value chain into various stages, depending on where they can achieve cost efficiency across different nations (Antràs and Chor, 2022). A deeper integration into GVC at the national level leads to enhanced economic growth (Pahl and Timmer, 2020). Moreover, integration of SMEs in the global value chain gives firms in the developing countries the opportunities to sustain in the long term, leading to stagnation in the domestic market (OECD, 2013). With participation in GVC, the firms are able to access the international markets, resulting in increased employment and income (World Bank, 2019). Firms that are a part of these large markets can invest in innovation and innovative activities to yield efficiency through technology transfer or Research and development. Moreover, as the engagement of the countries in the global value chain increases, it can facilitate SMEs’ integration in the GVC activities by engaging in small tasks, which may result in inclusive growth opportunities (UNCTAD, 2013).

The integration of the firms in GVCs varies among different countries, such as those in Sub-Saharan Africa and South America, which are mainly engaged in the initial phase of production, with limited product diversification and low value addition domestically. Conversely, Southeast Asian countries are actively involved in the processing of raw materials and assembly of industrial products. Malaysia, the Philippines and Thailand manufacture computers and other electronic devices. Whereas, China, Singapore, and South Korea manufacture components for mechanical components that are assembled in the developing countries. Additionally, Indonesia serves as a significant supplier of raw material to the value chains in the Asia-Pacific region (WTO, 2011). Over time, developing nations aspire to enhance their position in GVCs to reap greater economic advantages from the global production networks (Chikhun and Romanov, 2023).

Elevated tariffs, complexities of international trade may impede the participation of SMEs in the GVC (Dovis and Zaki, 2020). On the other hand, initiatives like trade liberalization, standardized regulations and simple, safe border crossings can help firms to integrate into the GVCs. (Regolo, 2017) has revealed that due to the geographical and cultural connections, new products are introduced in the market (Osabuohien et al., 2024). This may result in the progression of advanced trade patterns, perhaps leading to global and regional trade agreements.

Nevertheless, GVCs' integration of SMEs is significantly impeded by the lack of financial accessibility (Reddy et al., 2021; Urata and Baek, 2020), since it restricts firms' ability to invest in research and development, innovation, innovative activities and market expansion, which are quite elementary for GVC integration.

Several studies have previously examined the factors that affect firms' likelihood of entering the GVC; however, a significant gap still exists, especially related to the distinctive characteristics of the firms. The proposed study fills this gap by identifying the drivers and constraints for the firms, specifically for the developing countries. In this study, we tend to investigate the dimensions of the firms, the industry they belong to (service or manufacturing), since the previous studies have overlooked the theoretical and empirical evidence (Brancati et al., 2017).

These are the following research questions that we address in our study:

- 1) Does the size of the firm influence the likelihood of the firms' to integrate in GVC?
- 2) Does the sector to which the firm belongs affect GVC integration?
- 3) Does the regional variation influence the GVC participation for the firms?

The remaining section of the paper is organized as follows. Section II reviews both theoretical and empirical literature, and Section III provides the data source, methodology and a description of the variables. Section IV concludes and discusses the policy implications of our findings.

2. Theoretical underpinnings

This paper broadly relates to the theoretical literature on the factors that determine firms' participation in GVCs in general and their nature and likelihood of GVC participation in particular, and subsequently, their variations in developing countries. More specifically, the study is linked to the literature on factors determining a firm's integration in GVC (Fernandes et al., 2022; Urata and Baek, 2020). In the early 1980s, the traditional trade model was augmented to incorporate notions such as increasing returns to scale, product differentiation, and imperfect competition, which led to the emergence of 'new trade theory'. However, this approach has ignored the firm heterogeneity within sectors. Resulting in the development of the 'new' new trade theory, which aligns closely with Melitz's work and considers firm-level heterogeneity (Baldwin, 2005).

Our study emphasizes the new trade theory, which posits that the heterogeneity among firms affects their ability to participate in GVCs (Helpman et al., 2004; Melitz, 2003). This framework states that the firms with limited financial access are unable to invest in high-end activities due to substantial costs. Additionally, introducing firm heterogeneity in

international trade has provided valuable insights into how firms' characteristics affect the export behaviour (Helpman et al., 2004; Melitz, 2003). Based on this, the study provides these insights first: if the firms are competing locally, they are likely to perform better in the global market. Second, if a firm lacks geographical comparative advantages, it must gain a sufficient productivity level to enter the global markets.

3. Previous Literature

Studies in past have investigated the factors influencing GVC integration at both the firm and country levels. Factors such as factor endowment, political stability, liberalisation of trade policies, institutional quality and FDI inflows are the major country-specific factors that affect the GVC participation of the firm (Badr, 2019; Fernandes et al., 2022; OECD, 2013). On the other hand, several firm-specific factors that influence firms' participation in GVC are size of the firm, ownership, technological capabilities, access to finance, innovation and innovative activities (Antràs and Chor, 2022; Elshaarawy and Ezzat, 2023; Reddy and Sasidharan, 2021).

3.1. Drivers and Constraints of GVC Participation

The notion that only large firms can do business in foreign markets, whereas SMEs are only capable of operating within the country (Brazinskas and Beinoravičius, 2014), has faded with start-ups attempting to operate in the foreign market from their inception. The spread of industrial operations to wider areas through GVCs facilitates the involvement of SMEs and sub-suppliers in these international value networks (Kristensen and Lilja, 2011). The global expansion of firms and their potential impact on the economic well-being of the countries in which they operate have garnered growing interest. It is evident that the nature of the firm greatly influences the firm's participation in GVC (Brancati et al., 2017; Karakara and Osabuohien, 2024; Miao and Fortanier, 2018).

The evolution of GVC at the global, country, sectoral and firm level is well documented. As countries become more integrated into the Global production process, participation in the backwards linkages has risen. The levels and temporal changes in the GVC indicators vary widely across regions, countries and sectors. This section briefly reviews the studies that determine the GVC participation by firms. The results of the empirical findings are mixed. They are sensitive to methodology, country composition, sector and time coverage (Banerjee and Zeman, 2022). Harvie et al. (2010) were among the pioneers in this area, investigating a 2009 survey involving 780 companies with less than 200 employees across eight East Asian nations. Their definition of GVC participation includes firms that contribute to any segment of a production network and either import intermediate goods or export finished products. The probit analysis revealed that while the size of the firm did not affect initial entry, it played a significant role in advancement within the value chain;

concurrently, factors such as higher productivity, foreign ownership, improved access to finance, proactive innovation, and an entrepreneurial mindset substantially increased the likelihood of SME participation in GVCs (Urata and Baek, 2020).

Wignaraja (2013) expanded upon these findings by examining data from the World Bank Enterprise Survey, which encompassed 5,900 manufacturing firms across five ASEAN countries (Malaysia, Thailand, the Philippines, Indonesia, and Vietnam). He revealed that the age of the firm is negatively related to the GVC participation of the firm; on the contrary, firm size and foreign ownership, workers' education, foreign licenses, ISO certifications, and patents are significantly positive. Additionally, firms with improved financial access are likely to enhance and sustain GVC participation (Urata and Baek, 2020).

Urata and Baek (2021) suggested that labour productivity, firm size, ownership, and technological skills are the major factors determining a firm's participation in GVCs. Further, Gao and Zhang (2023); Singh and Kumar (2024) reveal that investing in digital soft infrastructure led to an increase in firms' integration from 9% to 20%, with pronounced effects visible for low-technology SMEs in SSA countries. However, Patel and Rao (2023) found that financial constraints continue to be a major constraint. Additionally, Chakraborty and Sahoo (2024) found that uncertainties in economic policy exacerbate these financial obstacles, decreasing the likelihood of GVC entry.

Nevertheless, Boffa et al, (2017) suggested that firm size and GVC integration demonstrate a positive relation to the competitiveness of firms and their involvement in GVC; they reveal that large firms are more inclined than smaller firms. Even smaller enterprises that are involved in GVC do so through connections with larger companies (OECD, 2019; World Bank, 2016). This occurs because GVC relies on the productivity, growth, financial accessibility, market influence, and trade capacity of firms of all sizes, and larger organizations can more readily obtain these capabilities compared to smaller firms.

Moreover, the financial viability of the firm is also a major enabler of GVC. Reddy and Sasidharan (2021) highlighted that inter-firm trade finance fosters GVC participation of Indian firms. Subsequently, firms depending on external finances hinder their participation in GVC, showing that financial constraints for firms are a major barrier for small firms. Similarly, Elshaarawy and Ezzat (2023) conclude that financially constrained firms have low innovation adaptability even when they participate in GVC, which is due to a lack of financial access. Nevertheless, firms having exposure to bank credits and banking facilities are more likely to participate in production chains to overcome liquidity shortages. This benefits the firms for long-term trading and helps better integrate with large firms in the

international market. Financial accessibility is an essential prerequisite for the firm integrating in the GVCs.

Studies reveal that the extent of foreign ownership visibly affects the level of GVC participation of the firm (Brancati et al., 2021; López-González and Kowalski, 2017). Moreover, it also facilitates the firm with a competitive edge, the capacity to attract international funds, to enhance their productivity, research and development, and it can further forge global connections and establish a network to expand into international markets (Benkovskis et al., 2020; Boffa et al., 2017; Rigo, 2021).

Studies suggest the legal status of the firm also influences the likelihood of GVC participation. Osabuohien et al. (2024) reveals that shareholding firms in Ghana and Nigeria are more likely to integrate in direct exports compared to sole proprietorships. Moreover, (de and Twum, 2020) proposed that firms with traded shares might be in a better positioned to reap the international investments, potentially enhancing their export activities and productivity. Shareholder firms in Rwanda are 18.5% more likely to be involved in GVCs compared to sole proprietorships, while partnership firms have 8.6% higher likelihood of being GVC firms than sole proprietorships, as noted by Karakara and Osabuohien (2024). Previous theoretical studies have concluded that having a shareholding structure improves a firm's sustainability by facilitating the issuance of shares for capital-raising, which in turn supports expansion and the acquisition of technology to enhance productivity for GVC participation (Antràs et al., 2017).

Additionally, Fernandes et al. (2022), Hewavitharana (2021), López-González and Kowalski (2017) suggest a positive correlation amongst firm's productivity and its integration in GVC, stating that lower per unit labour costs, in comparison to other factors, impact enterprises' engagement in GVCs. Karakara and Osabuohien (2024) concluded that improvements in firms' productivity, as measured by yearly sales is potentially significantly driven by the labour productivity, leads to an increase in the firm's likelihood of becoming a GVC in Nigeria by more than four times, while almost doubling the chances for firms in Rwanda.

Geographical location and digital connectivity are additional factors that are supposed to affect the GVC integration, as firms located in the export zones, industrial parks, and urban hubs are able to reap the benefits from the logistic capabilities that are helpful in managing internal operations (Karakara and Osabuohien, 2024). Additionally, the firms that are investing in ICT, such as websites and digital marketing, as it enhances their international visibility and competitiveness (Urata and Baek, 2020).

Despite the investments that firms are making, SMEs remain at a disadvantage in their efforts to integrate into the GVC, this is majorly because of lack of financial resources,

limited technology transfers, and informational asymmetries. Nevertheless, targeted policies such as trade facilitation, digital support, and financial accessibility, especially for the disadvantaged group can them to ensure more and better inclusive growth in the global trade.

3.2. Conceptual Underpinnings

The conceptual framework in Figure 1 illustrates that GVC participation of the firm is shaped by four major factors: first, firm size, second, sectoral characteristics, third, country characteristics, and fourth, nations’ policies. Firm size, country’s contextual factors significantly determine the likelihood of GVC integration. On the contrary, larger manufacturing firms that are located in business cities of a country with a robust economic structure and good access to financing would be more inclined to be a GVC firm.

Osabuohien et al. (2024), Montfaucon et al. (2022) and Kowalski et al. (2015) suggested that a country’s economic conditions influence the GVC participation of the firms. Additionally, Karakara and Osabuohien (2024) along with Antràs and Chor (2022) and Kuzmisiin and Kuzmisiinova (2017) highlighted that a company's industry and specific attributes affect its likelihood of engaging in GVC. The notion of country conditions aligns with earlier theories presented by Kurgman (1992) in his seminal work on geography and trade, he posits that a nation's geographical features influence its GVC engagement. Therefore, the economic climate, comprising financial systems and broader economic frameworks, as well as the characteristics of the industries in which companies operate, significantly affect their potential for participating in GVC.

Figure 1: Conceptual diagram

Source: Author’s own conceptualization.

4. Data and Methodology

4.1. Data

To document the factors affecting firms' participation in GVC, we extract firm-level data from the WBES database. The WBES consists of firm-level data from firms mainly in developing countries (low and middle-income countries). The survey mainly represents the firm-level data from the manufacturing and service sectors, and a few from the construction sector. Providing apt information about the firm-specific, sector-specific, and country-specific attributes, through various topics related to age, legal status, ownership, employment, business environment, access to finance, infrastructure, crime, corruption, and performance measures.

These surveys are conducted face-to-face with the managers of the firm, selected based on the stratified random sampling method, where the size of the economy and sector are used as strata. It follows a standardised questionnaire, which strengthens and endures a cross-country comparison of the data. Hence, our study period starts from 2006, and covers cross-sectional data for 123 developing economies corresponding to 1,47,740 firms (Please see Table A1 in the Appendix for the list of countries).

4.2. Methodology

Using the WBES database, the study analyses the factors that influence SMEs' participation in GVC in n developing countries. Following (Dovis and Zaki, 2020; Montfaucon et al., 2022; Osabuohien et al., 2024; Van Biesebroeck, Johannes and Mensah, Emmanuel Buadi, 2019), the participation of SMEs in GVCs is measured as firms engaging in export and import directly and indirectly (respectively). Thus, we employ a binary logistic model for the estimation. The logit model is employed for enhanced interpretability of results, providing parameter estimates that are asymptotically consistent, normally distributed, and efficient. T-tests are utilized for the equivalent of regression. Therefore, let P_i denote the likelihood of a firm integrating into Global Value Chains (GVC), for instance, by exporting its goods. Following (Osabuohien et al., 2024), the likelihood of non-participation in GVC is expressed as $1 - P_i$. We do not notice P_i due to Y being a latent variable. We see the outcome $Y = 1$ if the business participates in GVC by exporting its product, and $Y = 0$ if it does not; this establishes the model specification in equation (1):

$$GVC_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if firm export directly or indirectly} \\ & \text{and directly imports inputs and supplies} \\ 0 & \text{if otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Where, GVC_i is the Global value chain participation of the firm 'i'.

Legal Status of the Firms

Figure 2: Firms and Legal Status in Developing Countries (amongst the sample firms)

Source: Author’s Own, based on (World Bank Enterprises Survey, 2025).

Figure 3 reveals that among the large firms, the majority (47.85%) are engaged in direct export, while as low as 17.44% of the small-scale firms export directly in developing countries. Thus, shareholding and sole proprietorship firms in developing countries are seen to be more directly engaged in exporting. Correspondingly, Figure 4 shows the proportion of indirect export of the firm. the figure reveals that in developing countries, more of approx. 85% firms are engaged in indirect export. Prior research (Cusolito, Safadi, and Taglioni, 2016; Miao and Fortanier, 2018; OECD, 2019; Osabuohien et al., 2024; Karakara et al., 2025) concluded that firm size significantly influences participation in global value chains (GVCs), revealing heterogeneous trade patterns and impacts between small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and larger firms, with SMEs engaging indirectly in GVCs through exports facilitated by larger domestic or multinational corporations. In nutshell, 24,078 firms in developing countries are more engaged in exports.

GVC participation by firms

Figure 3: Export, SMEs, Developing country

Source: Author’s Own based on (World Bank Enterprises Survey, 2025).

Figure 4: Import, SMEs, Developing country

Source: Author’s Own based on (World Bank Enterprises Survey, 2025).

In figure 4, we observe that the import of supplies and inputs in developing countries. It reveals that most of the large-scale firms (60.87%) import their inputs or supplies for production. A similar trend is observed among medium firms.

Further, to examine the pattern of engagement in foreign trade for the listed firms. Among 1,79,615 sample firms, 58,207 firms or 32.41% of the firms are engaged in foreign trade, 68,690 firms of the total firms are engaged in export but not import; 24,078 firms out of 68,690 are involved in direct and indirect exports but not imports. Figure 5, however, reveals that 34,129 firms are involved in imports procurements and supplies 17,148 firms are engaged in both imports and exports and are considered as “GVC firms”. It is evident that as we include imports and exports, both the share decreases to 24.96%, indicating that a major portion of the firms do not participate in foreign trade.

The proportion of firms engaging in GVC increases as the size of the firm increases (Urata and Baek 2020, The determinants of GVC participation in GVC: A cross-country firm level analysis) indicating that firms with less than 199 employees face more obstacles/challenges to integrating into GVC.

Table 5: Firm Size, GVC and non-GVC Participation of the Firms

Source: Author’s Own based on (World Bank Enterprises Survey, 2025).

We analysed the distribution of GVC and non-GVC firms across firm type, legal status and region-wise across the developing countries, Figures 5, 6 and 7, respectively, through

the pictorial case of this analysis. The trends from these figures reveal interesting insights that medium-scale firms (15,329) generally engage in GVC participation, while a similar trend is observed with large firms. However, small firms are less engaged in GVCs due to their constraints in accessing finance, non-financial resources, and size.

Figure 6: Legal Status, GVC and non-GVC Participation of the Firms

Source: Author’s Own based on (World Bank Enterprises Survey, 2025).

Among the shareholding firms, the maximum number of firms are engaged in GVC (small- 3,168 firms, medium=5,106, large=4,929 firms), while sole proprietorship has the least number of GVC participating firms (only 1380 firms).

Table 7: Region-wise GVC and non-GVC Firms in Developing Countries

Source: Author’s Own based on (World Bank Enterprises Survey, 2025).

The GVC and non-GVC distribution of firms regionally, out of 21,565 GVC participation sample firms, the figure 8, shows that large firms Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC) region is more engaged in GVC in comparison to other regions, Sub-Saharan Africa (AFR), East Asia and Pacific (EAP), Europe and Central Asia (ECA), Middle East and North Africa (MNA), South Asia (SAR) while other small-scale firms in AFR and LAC are more engaged in GVCs.

5. Result and Discussion

Table 2, presents the descriptive statistics and the distribution of the variables across all developing countries in the study. The majority of businesses have been in operation for over five years. Over 98% of enterprises in developing countries have existed for over five years. This indicates that the enterprises in these countries are quite prominent. In these countries, over 69 per cent of enterprises are owned by men. However, female ownership is also emerging, as over 30 per cent of firms are owned by females.

Table 2: Distribution of variables and descriptive statistics

Descriptive and Distribution of Variables			Number and Percentage of Variables	
Variable	Measurement	Reponses	Developing Countries	
			Percentage	Observations
Age of the Firms	Number of years the firm has operated	Less than/equal 5 years	0.83	1,521.00
		Greater than 5 years	98.62	1,80,726.00
Gender of the firm owner	Gender of the owner of the firm	Female	30.31	53,601.00
		Male	69.69	1,23,263.00
Gender of the top manager	Gender of the top manager of the firm	Female	14.90	23,282.00
		Male	84.73	1,32,433.00
Legal Status of the Firms	The legal status the of firm	Shareholding	39.20	71,861.00
		Sole Proprietorship	39.47	72,341.00
		Partnership	19.32	35,413.00
competition	Firms compete with other informal firms	Yes	45.82	77,818.00
		No	49.40	83,886.00
Managerial experience	Top manager's years of experience in the firm's field		18.28 [^]	
Subsidiary firm	The firm is part of a larger firm	Yes	83.19	1,49,531
		No	16.81	30,216
Firm type	Number of employees the firm has (this shows the size of the firm)	Small scale	47.21	86,538
		Medium scale	33.39	61,202
		Large scale	19.40	35,559
Foreign ownership	Whether the firm has foreign ownership	Yes	12.05	22,089
		No	87.95	1,61,210
Sector firm operates	The sector where the firms operate	Manufacturing	53.37	97,818
		Service	46.63	85,481
Export indirect	The firm exports through another firm	Yes	8.36	15,323
		No	91.64	1,67,976
Export direct	The firm exports its products directly	Yes	14.60	26,765
		No	85.40	1,56,534
import inputs or supplies	Whether the firm directly imports inputs/supplies	Yes	33.35	61,123
		No	38.35	70,293
GVC	The firm is a GVC one	Yes	21.12	38,713
		No	73.59	1,34,887

Source: Author's own calculation, Note: [^]= Mean value

The number of enterprises with male top managers exceeded those with female top managers. Around 84% of enterprises are led by males. This significantly shows that the

enterprises are predominantly male-controlled regarding ownership and senior management positions. Fernandes et al. (2022) asserted that men exhibit a higher propensity to initiate enterprises.

The legal status of enterprises across several nations indicates that shareholding, sole proprietorship constituted the predominant form of business ownership in developing countries. The firms are competing in almost equal numbers of firms with formal and informal firms competing more (49.40%). Additionally, the average duration of management experience was 18 years. The experience of senior executives may facilitate firms' growth and development, enabling their entry into the global market.

The ownership of firms reveals that the majority of enterprises globally are domestically owned, with around 12% exhibiting foreign ownership. In the industry sector (manufacturing or service), 53% of enterprises in developing countries operate within the manufacturing sector, while 46.63% of enterprises are service sector firms.

These firms possessed the highest percentage of engagement in direct exports (85.40%). They have a lower percentage of enterprises engaged in indirect exports, at 8.36%. Around 33 per cent of the firms are importing inputs and supplies from other countries. In each country, the number of enterprises that export directly is more than those that export indirectly. However, in all the countries, fewer than 21% of the enterprises were engaged in GVCs. This may apply to numerous enterprises that import raw materials and supplies but exclusively sell their products domestically. Badr (2019) concluded similar results, who investigated that the firms in Sub-Saharan Africa utilize imported inputs while selling their products in the domestic market.

6. Conclusion

In this study, we investigated the characteristics of firms classified as small, medium, and large within their respective sectors, as well as the influence of these classifications on the participation of firms in GVCs within the developing nations. We employed the Enterprise Survey (ES) from the World Bank database, which pertains to individual firms. The findings suggest that the participation of firms in GVC is significantly and favourably influenced by variables such as firm size, legal status, productivity, access to ICTs (internet and website), financial accessibility, and the managerial experience of senior management. But the gender of the business owner and the senior management did not affect the business's participation in the GVC.

The government should facilitate firms' access to ICT infrastructure, according to our perspective. This would facilitate the firms in the global market and help them to access international investment. Additional assistance will be required for small businesses to expand and capitalize on the economies of scale and scope that are inherent in larger

organizations. Furthermore, it is recommended that companies be encouraged to engage in ownership and partnership arrangements, as these environments are conducive to the development of creativity and innovative ideas. This will incentivize these companies to participate in GVC.

Furthermore, literature has demonstrated that manufacturing sectors exhibit faster growth rates when they engage in global value chains (GVCs) from an export perspective (backward linkages), whereas service sectors exhibit faster growth rates when they utilize imported intermediate goods to produce goods for export (forward linkages). As a result, governments and businesses in the study country should closely consider all of these characteristics when considering the possibility of joining GVCs in order to develop the most effective business strategies. For example, SMEs may establish sales subsidiaries in other countries or adapt their industrial operations to be more international in order to directly target foreign markets.

The results of this study may be more effective when applied to the developing countries that were examined, and they may not apply to industrialized nations. For improved comprehension, future research should concentrate on panel data that could clarify causal relationships among variables. Furthermore, in order to ascertain the variables of the study, additional researchers may analyse the empirical data sector by sector.

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Appendix 1: List of Countries and Number of firms in Developing countries

Countries	Firms	Countries	Firms	Countries	Firms	Countries	Firms
Afghanistan	945	El Salvador	2,501	Mauritius	751	Tanzania	1,832
Angola	1,215	Equatorial Guinea	173	Mexico	4,282	Thailand	1,000
Antigua and barbuda	151	Eritrea	179	Micronesia	68	Timor-Leste	514
Argentina	3,108	Eswatini	613	Mongolia	1,082	Togo	453
Armenia	1,655	Ethiopia	1,492	Morocco	2,101	Tonga	300
Azerbaijan	1,363	Fiji	164	Mozambique	1,080	Trinidad and Tobago	484
Bahamas	150	Gabon	179	Myanmar	1,239	Tunisia	1,852
Bahrain	150	Gambia	487	Namibia	1,216	Turkiye	5,575
Bangladesh	3,944	Georgia	1,906	Nepal	1,432	Turkmenistan	311
Barbados	303	Ghana	1,927	Nicaragua	1,147	Uganda	1,325
Belize	150	Grenada	153	Niger	301	Uruguay	1,935
Benin	664	Guatemala	1,457	Nigeria	4,567	Uzbekistan	3,003
Bhutan	658	Guinea	373	Pakistan	3,482	Vanuatu	239
Bolivia	1,339	Guinea Bissau	159	Panama	969	Venezuela	820
Botswana	1,232	Guyana	165	Papua New Guinea	210	Viet Nam	3,077
Brazil	1,802	Honduras	1,128	Paraguay	1,716	Yemen	830
Burkina Faso	774	Hong Kong SAR China	598	Peru	3,622	Zambia	1,805
Burundi	427	India	18,657	Philippines	3,663	Zimbabwe	1,199
Cabo Verde	319	Indonesia	5,719	Rwanda	1,171		
Cambodia	1,364	Iraq	1,775	Samoa	266		
Cameroon	1,339	Jamaica	591	Saudi Arabia	1,573		
Central African Rep..	301	Jordan	1,766	Senegal	1,710		
Chad	467	Kazakhstan	3,603	Seychelles	103		
Chile	2,050	Kenya	2,439	Sierra Leone	511		
China	4,889	Kosovo	743	Singapore	623		
Colombia	3,854	Kyrgyz Republic	1,219	Solomon Islands	151		
Congo	516	Lao PDR	1,693	South Sudan	895		
Costa Rica	895	Lebanon	1,093	South Africa	2,034		
Côte d'Ivoire	1,536	Lesotho	451	Sri Lanka	610		
DRC	2,253	Liberia	301	St Kitts and Nevis	150		
Djibouti	266	Madagascar	1,379	St Lucia	150		
Dominica	150	Malawi	673	St Vincent and Grenadi	154		
Dominican Republic	719	Malaysia	3,200	Sudan	662		
Ecuador	1,730	Mali	1,427	Suriname	385		
Egypt	7,786	Mauritania	387	Tajikistan	1,435		

Source: Author's Own, based on (World Bank Enterprises Survey, 2025).

Appendix2: Firms in developing countries according to their size

Firm Size	Number of Firms
Small (<20)	86,538
Medium (20-99)	61,202
Large (100 And over)	35,559

Source: Author's Own, based on (*World Bank Enterprises Survey*, 2025).

Appendix 3: firm size and their legal status

Firm Size	Shareholding	Partnership	Sole Proprietorship	Total
Small (<20)	23,782	14,251	47,058	85,091
Medium (20-99)	27,335	13,404	19,023	59,762
Large (100 and over)	20,744	7,758	6,260	34,762

Appendix 4: Export and import, GVC and non-GVC firms in the given sample

Firm Size	No GVC Participation	Either Import or Export	Both Import and Export
Small(<20)	59,557	23,279	3,702
Medium(20-99)	34,180	19,618	7,404
Large (100 and Over)	13,519	11,581	10,459